

Theoretical Inspection and Rethink of Marketing Mix

Ismat Ara Eti & Md. Murshedul Bari

Abstract:

The world is relentlessly changing which creating new trades. A few ages past, speediness of these revolutions, maybe it was every fasten of years or every decade, but straightaway, every year or every month we are nearsighted new goods and products that in the history there was not any kind of them. Every company should not neglect to take virtuous maintenance of customers that helps to partake the right planning and aiming people, the right product or service, right place or distribution, right price, right promotion, right physical and psychological evidence, with the right amount of productivity & quality performance in carrying the Ps of Marketing. This paper aims to undertake an extensive literature review from the past studies related to the concept of the marketing mix and descriptive analysis is used to analyze the best practice among the 8Ps or more Ps of marketing mix towards business performance. Equally, a tool of marketing strategy and theoretical framework grants a view of different theories of marketing mix where marketers should be considered before launching a product. Firms should plan a targeted approach on these different components which help the firm in formulating strategic decisions. The study provides managers with theoretical guidance and concept on how the marketing mix will improve the organization's performance.

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Literature Review

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Introduction

Every target market incorporates a unique marketing combination to set the needs of targeted customers and meet the company's goals. All strategies must be combined with other strategies. Therefore, the marketing mix is very similar to its part. The integration of marketing is among those basic marketing ideas and its incomprehensible development for those who want more marketing knowledge which is the axiom of architecture and teaching in the field. However, in contrast to many marketing theories, this concept is reminiscent of an indisputable pillar of marketing and practice theory (Silverman, 1995). The key factors that make marketing integration a powerful one are: marketing seems easy to deal with with the availability of this framework. It also delegates professional marketing activities and separates the marketing background from other organizational activities. And the ingredients of the marketing mix can be very helpful in changing the competitive landscape of a company (Gummesson, 1994). Progress has also transformed the industry through institutions and companies to address problems and tasks, and competitors, and each institution must adopt policies regarding long-term vision, purpose, objectives and opportunities and arrangements (Borden, 1964). The marketing combination is based on a single P (price) microeconomic theory (Chong, 2003). McCarthy (1964) offered a "marketing mix", often referred to as "4Ps", as a way of interpreting marketing planning done (Bennett, 1997). Marketing integration is not a scientific concept, but simply a framework that identifies key decision-making managers in preparing their offerings to meet customer needs. The main purpose of this review paper is to clarify the theoretical details of the marketing mix and its dynamics. Other objectives are to identify the importance of the marketing mix, the pros and cons that will help any business in understanding ideas and introducing new products in the future.

Marketing Mix History

Many researchers have tried to differentiate and introduce a new and more accurate Ps to the existing framework. This process has been going on for a long time now since the new Ps continued to emerge due to the changing commercial environment. This paper seeks to review the existing frameworks of commercial combinations. The beginning of 4 Ps where all can be drawn in the early 1940s (Groucutt, J., Leadley, P., & Forsyth, P. 2004b). The first approved speech for the merger has already been honoured by Harvard University Marketing Professor, Prof. James Culliton (Banting, P. M., & Ross, R. E. 1973). In 1948, 'Marketing Cost Management' was an article with a surprising invention when author Culliton described retailers as 'ingredient mixers' (Culliton, J. W., 1948). Encouraging the article published by Culliton, his colleague Professor Neil Borden published an illustrative article describing the first record of the marketing mix. Thereafter, he exaggerated by spreading the idea that 'marketing is integrated' (Borden, B. & N. H. 1964). Giving Borden's account, he used the term, 'marketing mix' little by little since the late 1940s. As such, he is notorious for using the word 'marketing mix' in his presidential address given to him by the American Marketing Association in 1953 (Dominici, G., 2009). By the late 1960s, retailers would not have been able to obtain real consent as to what items should be included in the mix of advertisers' concept as 'mixed ingredients' (Van Waterschoot & Van Den Bulte, 1992). The modern structure of 4 Ps which was first proposed in 1960 by E. Jerome McCarthy provided them with a management approach that protects analytics, consumer performance, market research, market segregation, and planning (McCarthy, 1960). During the basic AMA Summit presented to Services Marketing in the early 1980s, the idea of extending marketing mixing began to embrace and evolve into theoretical

works and also identified many important limitations of the 4 Ps model (Fisk, Brown, & Bitner, 1993). During that conference, the papers that introduced service vendors considered a review of standard marketing mixes designed to take into account that services were very different from the products that are most needed to deal with different strategies. In 1981, Booms and Bitner recommended a 7 Ps model containing the first 4 Ps enhanced process, people and tangible evidence, as the most important presence in service marketing (Booms & Bitner, 1981). Especially since the 1980s, some new introductions have been made into a marketing mix. The fifth P-People was nominated by Judd (1987). Booms and Bitner (1980) introduced 3 new Ps (process, participants, and tangible evidence) in the existing 4 Ps to make the marketing mix framework work in services. Kotler (1984) recommended an increase in the construction of public opinion and political power in existing 4Ps. Goldsmith (1999) recommends 8Ps (product, price, location, promotions, customization, participants, process, and tangible evidence).

Theoretical Inspection of Marketing Mix

The marketing mix consists of four products which are product, price, promotion. By submitting the organization's resources to be provided with products and services on behalf of the organization concerned will ultimately achieve the goals. (Bennett, 1997). The term "marketing integration" called the hotchpotch of elements helps in the pursuit of a particular market reunification. Accelerating the effective use of the concept should be robust in performance problems (Van Waterschoot and Van Den Bulte, 1992). Services require another type of marketing and a modified type of marketing integration. As a result, they differentiate between product marketing and product advertising. In their marketing mix, three Ps namely staff, material assets, and processes are added, and finally, 7Ps are formed. (Culliton, 1948). Robicheaux (1976) found that important marketing policies changed significantly when prices were considered the most important marketing activity. Based on an explanation that focuses on marketing the concept of 4Ps has been criticized, but not designed for customers (Popovic, 2006). Of the two benefits of a marketing mix, the first is an important tool used to make one see the sales manager's work with the benefit of his competitive power in the marketing mix compared to the profit of others and the second benefit of being helpful in revealing another aspect of marketing manager work (Goi, 2009). All managers must specify the resources available between the various needs and competing devices for the marketing mix. Therefore, this will help to unlock the marketing philosophy of the organization (Low & Tan, 1995).

Importance of Marketing Mix

According to research by Ahuja (2016) and Basin (2018), there are some important factors and the importance of a marketing mix that has a significant business impact. The market-affiliated company must be protected that marketing materials that combine stops are efficient and effective because they play an important role in changing trends. A marketing mix that has all the P's are well matched where the price should fit well with the product or product placement should go well with the promotion. All the P's are connected transforming a series of solid bonds. With these bonds, it creates a seamless marketing mix for the product. Each product has a unique advertising combination that can be categorized by a new product. If a business wants to increase product lines and lengths, they should make small changes that can be product characteristics, a price that creates a product portfolio. Physical evidence as an integral part of a marketing mix that can be very effective in restaurants or local building businesses. By analyzing competitors' marketing mixes, it helps to identify competitors' weaknesses and help build better corporate product growth. A well-prepared

company is also prepared in the event of a disaster. As a force, such a company needs to understand all P's in depth. There are many options but marketing analysis is the best way to be strong and the ROI may be high now.

Pros and Cons of Marketing Mix

In an integrated way, many businesses that work with and write the implementation of P policies remain the work of various departments and individuals within the organization. (Constantinides, 2002). Möller (2006) emphasized the suspension of 4Ps marketing integration, similarly, the obelisk of ancient commercial management becomes a victim of strong criticism. These criticisms can be summed up (Fakeideas, 2008) as a commercial combination that does not believe in customer behavior but is directed at the inside and respects customers as inactive; does not allow communication and cannot take relationships. Marketing combinations do not have a cheap personalized transactional marketing system. Different aspects of service marketing can be considered through marketing mixes. The product is announced in unison but many organizations do not sell the product lightly. Where retailers sell product lines or trademarks are all linked to the buyer's perspective. Relationship building has become a major marketing focus or consumer experience that can be announced by a marketing mix. The concept of market integration has not been addressed to advertisers who are considered important. According to a study by Marketing Evolution (2020), traditionally by increasing marketing power, it will help to move beyond the marketing system, including Individual-level, behavioral data, have ideas that will contribute to the sale of leading channels, Impact of product authority suitable for use in each marketing media, Creative messages have an impact on all channels, Sources of posting of marketing notes

Six Powerful Elements of Marketing Mix

Product: Product is promoted in the market to reduce demand or demand, as well as tangible goods, services, skills, events, people, places, buildings, organizations, information and ideas. The product of information can be physically understood and presented to meet the needs and attractiveness of the market (Kotler & Keller, 2012). A service is something that can be an effort, a profit or satisfaction offered for a sale. It is unexplained and will not lead to the management of anything (Kotler & Armstrong, 2012). A product is defined as a product or service for consumers who are interested in paying for it. Includes material components, and intangible products, such as services, consumer goods (Singh, 2012). According to the Chartered Institute of Marketing (2009), in juxtaposes, an efficient company will find that customers need or want. After searching, proceed with the right product with the right level of quality to meet the needs from this time on. A flawless product should deliver customer value. This figure represents eyewitnesses. The product goes without physical insurance that can be a product. The product must have two items described below.

Five product levels: Kotler and Keller (2012) suggested that the five product levels reflect the overall product as detailed as the primary product refers to problem-solving services or core benefits that assist customers when purchasing a product. A standard product is a product version that contains only those attributes or features that are required to operate. The expected product contains a set of adjectives or features that consumers usually expect and agree on when purchasing a product. Additional product refers to any product variation, additional features, or services that help differentiate the product from its competitors. A potential product includes all product additions and modifications that you may encounter in

the future. To ensure customer loyalty in the future, the business should aim to surprise and delight customers in the future by continuing to add products.

Figure 1 Five Product Levels Kotler and Keller, 2012, p.326)

- **Product life cycle:** At the stage of product development, sales are zero and investment costs amount. When in the introduction stage, slow sales growth and profits are fictional. After that at the growth stage, rapid market acceptance, and increasing profits. When product at the maturity stage, the slowdown in sales growth and profits level off or decline. At the final stage, product decline product sales fall off and profits drop.

Figure 2 Sales and profits over the product's life from inception to demise Kotler et al, 2013, p.337)

Price: Price is the amount of money indicated for a product or service. It is the sum of values that customers interchange for the settlements of having or using the product or service. Authors quantified that the prices ought to be based on the perceptions of consumers in contradiction of value received. But it should not on the cost of the seller and producers (Kotler & Armstrong, 2012). The price is the ultimate element that has a great impact on the services marketing mix (Lovelock & Wirtz, 2011). Kotler et al. (2005) wrote cost-based pricing is the naivest pricing strategy whereby using this strategy price is set by tallying some mark-up to the cost of the product. This strategy works only if the firm's prices are not too extreme as equal to the competition. Another cost-oriented pricing strategy is called Break-even Pricing. With this strategy, firms conclude the price as a result firms can recapture manufacturing and marketing cost, or make an aimed profit. (Nagle, Hogan & Zale, 2016). Again, Kotler et al. (2005) show that competition-based pricing is creating conditions when a company sets prices by the competition. Prices are fundamentally centered on the prices of the competitors and in customer- value-based pricing, products are priced on the foundation of the superficial value of the product. Bestowing to the Chartered Institute of

Marketing (2009) the price needs to be economical, this does not point that means the cheapest because it is the only element of the marketing mix that spawns revenue. Furthermore, pricing should take the following factors such as fixed and variable costs, competition, company objectives, proposed positioning, and target group. An organization can embrace many pricing strategies where the pricing strategy will usually be centred on corporate aims. As like as effective product development, distribution, and promotion breakthrough the organization success where efficient pricing master plan is the harvest (Avlonitis & Indounas, 2005). Among the other elements, effective pricing strategy not entirely compensated for poor effecting but from financial good achievement, abortive pricing be able to go those works (Nagle & Holden 2002).

Place: To make the product or service accessible for use or use by the consumer or customer channels for business sets of independent supporting organizations. Distribution channels are an important part of the delivery of products or services. To get a better trade speed helps service delivery and time are the key factors that can add value to consumers (Kotler & Armstrong, 2012). However, storage costs, inventory, and distribution costs are at the right level, the product must be delivered in the right place, at the right time and in the right quantity. Also, location means displaying a product at customer meetings. This can be in a store window or online (Chartered Institute of Marketing, 2009). Easy-to-use and easy-to-distribute distribution contracts for products and services that are aware of the reputation of distribution channels based on various types of organizations (Jones, 2003). The distribution channel is categorized as an integral part of the service, which includes service providers, mediators, and a consistent service user (Gattorna, 1978). A small distribution channel consisting of very few buyers in a restricted market area and with a long distribution channel contains multiple loading areas to deliver products (Djafar, Amer, and Lee, 2013).

Promotion: The company uses a credible amount of customer communication and builds customer relationships through a combination of promotional or marketing which is a specific combination of promotional tools. Promoting or hotchpotch marketing communications made up of five communication models is key: advertising, marketing promotion, personal marketing, social relations, and direct marketing (Kotler & Armstrong, 2012). Some authors suggest eight types of communication namely: advertising, marketing promotion, events and experiences, public relations and information, direct marketing, affiliate marketing, oral marketing, and personal marketing (Kotler & Keller, 2012). A promotion is a way in which a company communicates what it does and can offer a suggestion to customers. Contains activities such as branding, advertising, PR, corporate ownership, marketing management, special offers, and exhibitions. Coffman (2002) emphasizes that social interaction is essential to internal and external communication. Therefore, public relations activities can help achieve goals related to the company's reputation and market confidence, but the company needs to anticipate and select appropriate communication channels, viz. Promotional action groups include newsletters, newsletters, press conferences, authorized views of these deliveries (Kotler & Mindak, 1978). GÜREL, E. (2016) shows that exhibitions and exhibitions. Advertisement "word of mouth" - is where information about a company is passed on to business employees, customers, etc., without the use of media or other external communication channels (Papasolomou, et al., 2014). Indirect exhibits are the company's "unintentional" assets, film services, theatre, and television broadcasts (Sundstrom, B., 2012).

People (Personnel): Employee is an empty object that brings customers to services where employees get acquainted with customers directly. These types of organizations are trying to find a market position to train their employees in marketing and how to treat customers (Yasanallah & Bidram, 2012b). According to the authors, human variables are divided into staffs that act as cleaners, security managers, and store staff (Kirkup & Rafiq 1999, Warnaby, Bennison & Davies, 2005). Tracking people from senior marketing staff to the Managing Director of all companies depends on the people. In addition, marketing will be great with employees the secret of the organization that having the right person in the right place is important because it also shows that retailers should view consumers as people who will understand their lives amazingly, not just as they shop for consumer products and services (AHUJA, 2016). Those who interact with customers convey an idea and develop a profound impact that can either be positive or positive or perhaps to customer satisfaction. The reputation of the product depends on the hands of the people. (IChartered Institute of Marketing, 2009).

Process: Procedures are essential to delivering a service that is potentially unpopular. The process of illustrating the design of the app appears to be reliable in the target area (Kar, 2019). The process is one of the most neglected 'P's. Issues such as call waiting times for customers to get more time to sit and listen to a recorded message before reaching the company. As a result, customers who will stop travel efforts will develop negative perceptions of others because of the negative process (Chartered Institute of Marketing, 2009). The process reflects all the ingenuity, discipline, and structure that prioritises marketing management. In the marketplace, retailers should avoid complex planning and decision-making and establish appropriate processes (AHUJA, 2016). This process brings about a structured process in which any strong company and customers are present to cooperate and fulfill their roles most effectively in market marketing (Wickham, 2009). Process management that ensures the availability and sustainability and efficiency of services where the mix of marketing is a balance of service demand and service. By making rocket a process of providing customer service, organizations can tarnish the field of consumer intimacy that results from a purchase and ultimately increase sales (Yasanallah & Bidram, 2012b).

Physical Evidence: Physical evidence takes away customer satisfaction when it hurts the part of the guards and calculates the quality of the experience by using other methods and its services are intangible, customers rely on other contribution judgment indicators (Kar, 2019). household items, symbols, uniforms, business cards, warranties, etc. to indicate the category of donations (Wickham, 2009). The tangible assets that reflect the eco-friendly power needed by companies to provide services to customers can increase consumer preferences by offering skills such as self-service, large shelves, etc. as major in-store options that can prevent consumer movement without any purchase (Yasanallah & Bidram, 2012b). The physical evidence presented by the organization must confirm the client's thoughts. Before buying customers have no experience, so they get information from others by looking at the services. That customer's comments are trustworthy due to the initial purchase. Some companies seek feedback from these customers to promote the index to encourage new customers to shop with a higher level of trust (Chartered Institute of Marketing, 2009).

Productivity and Quality Performance

Ensuring the level of service required is provided to the consumer with a strong respect for customer expectations throughout the purchase event (Wickham, 2009). It has been shown that the overall profitability of a company can be greatly affected by focusing not only on the top line by improving sales but also on focusing on the bottom line by reducing the overall cost of service delivery. In service management, the variable costs are usually much higher than the planned costs, so additional costs, if properly managed, can have a significant impact on productivity. Productivity development is an important part of cost management defined by integrated service management but quality, as defined by the customer, is critical for the service to differentiate itself from other suppliers (Kar, 2019). The 8th P of Service Marketing has taken place in the so-called Production and Quality or Performance study which is also described as global marketing, helping to replace potential outcomes such as financial and non-financial effects of immediate profit as well as product and customer equity elsewhere, for example, social responsibility, moral, and social. Also established in research such a process is increasing to bring better balance and quality to jobs. Quality assurance is a distinguishing factor in service management and long-term support (AHUJA, 2016).

Is there any P also?

In some fields of thought, there is a P of Marketing Mix. This Extended Marketing Mix is described below in detail. The early 1960s then 4Ps of marketing were held when the higher payment process relied on cash, check, and credit card. The authors have indicated that there is little possibility or opportunity to use a credit card at that time. Nowadays, there are many payment methods that are accessible due to technological advances as the authors claim that payment is a real part of the mix of advertising (Shevlin, 2012 & Fetter, 2012). According to a study by Larry (2017) it shows 3 Ps where the first P is partners which shows that Alliances works with others other than the organizations for which the risk and profit is shared. Another P presentation is an action show for customers, suppliers, vendors, vendors, vendors, sales mediators, clients, employees, partners. Extra P is a desire when other strong or extreme emotions have feelings for planning, construction, pricing, promotion, co-operation, sales and the full marketing of products or services. Also, Morris (2018) states that there are two other Pss in the Marketing mix which is portfolio and project.

Conclusion

This report is an overview of the past, present, and future of the Marketing Mix According to the literature review, marketing Mix (MM) is the well- disciplined group of variables that the organization may use to affect the customer's responsibility. Promotional tools depend upon the type of product, the price which will be charged for the product and the procedure through which it would reach to the customer furthermore while deciding the price of a product; the important things to consider are manufacturing cost of the product, promotion cost and amount incurred on distribution channels. Productivity in this regard is always combined with quality – supply of the best quality every time. Each organization aims to build up such a structure of 4P's, which can make customer satisfaction's highest level and meet its organizational objectives at the same time. However, notwithstanding limitations, this study has contributed toward the existing literature by indicating that identified marketing mixes such as physical evidence, process, place, and people have a positive and significant effect on marketing. The major findings of this study that marketing mix has

more powerful elements that are all under consideration in business. Marketing mix has tremendous impact on business based on consumer demand. Thus, this study is gathered to hold over in mind the needs of customers. Even after 80 years, the marketing mix is still very much applicable to a marketer's day to day work. A good marketer will learn to adapt the theory to fit with not only modern times but their business model. Future research is suggested to measure the theoretical consequence of known marketing mix elements for the understanding of knowledge performance.

Declaration of Conflicting Interest

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research authorship and publication of the research.

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